

Timber beams reinforced with fiber-reinforced polymer: advanced wood engineering

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Abstract

In recent years, studies have focused on alternative materials for structural reinforcement, and much attention has been devoted to the use of fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP). This material has high strength, low weight, corrosion resistance and electromagnetic neutrality, which makes FRP a suitable candidate in many structural applications, especially the reinforcement of timber beams. This article was carried out to study the effect of reinforcing timber beams with fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) on their bending behavior, such as ultimate bending strength, bearing capacity, deflection ductility and rigidity. The results provided through the literature review showed that the ultimate bending strength of the beam increases to 63% (it depends on the technique of reinforcing FRP with timber). In contrast, mid-span deflection decreases, resulting in higher stiffness values (between 31% and 64%). On the other hand, the deflection ductility of a reinforced timber beam is increased to 51% when the FRP/timber beam ratios are respected.

Keywords: Timber beam, fiber-reinforced polymers, wood engineering, tensile strength, ductility, bending strength.

Introduction

Timber is one of the oldest known building materials. Moreover, it is the only naturally renewable building material. For many centuries, it has been the natural building material for houses and other buildings, for bridges and riverside structures...etc. Several factors have led to the popularity of this material in construction; its lightness, durability, simplicity of manufacture, and its reusability. There are also some natural flaws that can reduce its structural strength, such as knots, splits, and checks. In addition, various environmental factors can cause timber to degrade over time. Structural elements may need to be reinforced because of possible natural disasters or during use. Beams are elements under load in the direction perpendicular to their axes. They are therefore essentially under the effect of bending.

The study of the behavior of the beams during bending tests has shown that the lower face of the material generally yields. For this reason, reinforcement techniques are used to improve the strength of the beam elements. In traditional reinforcement techniques, metal is generally recommended for timber structures. It is inevitable that steel reinforcements will require maintenance over time, create visual pollution in the reinforced areas and bring additional load to the structure, plus steel bands lack lightness, flexibility and corrosion (KILINÇARSLAN and TÜRKER 2020).

In recent years, composite technologies have become increasingly prevalent in the mechanical and engineering industries. Increasing the durability of timber through the introduction of new composite materials and related technical knowledge helps to achieve the desired engineering properties. Fiber Reinforced Polymer (FRP) reinforcement is one of the recent methods used to repair existing wood structures or to create high performance structures in newly built wood structures, due to its characteristics of lightness, wear resistance, flexibility and its uses will not affect the appearance of wood (Wang et al. 2020). The main intention of the work is to investigate the feasibility of reinforcing timber beams with fiber reinforced polymer composites, and to examine the effect of bond geometries on the ultimate flexural capacity, stiffness, deflection and ductility.

Materials and methods

Based on recent literature reviews, this study consists in analyzing, on the one hand, fiber-reinforced polymers as a composite material and their properties. On the other hand, to investigate the effect of its reinforcement with timber beams, on their bending behavior such as bearing capacity, ductility and bending strength.

1. Fiber Reinforced Polymer Composite Material

Materials created by combining two or more components that are macro-different from one another across an interface are referred to be composite materials (Jones 2000). The majority of the qualities of the constituent parts of the composite material are still present. FRP reinforcement consists of fibers that are bonded together by a polymer resin (matrix) (Fig.1).

Fig.01. Constituents of Fiber Reinforced Polymers Materials.

Source. Introduction to Composite Materials.2018

It comes in the form of strips or fabrics. Slats, a pull-extruded composite, offer the advantage of better manufacturing and installation control, but can only be used on a flat surface. Fabrics, much more flexible, can be used on almost any surface (flat, round, oval, etc.) (Cheung and Carey 2017).

1.1 Fiber's production and proprieties

Fibers are the main element of the composite, have a diameter between 5 and 15 μ m (Guichard et al. 2018). They can be unidirectional (slats, fabrics) or bidirectional (tissues) and have characteristics specific to each. Among the most used fibers are carbon (PRFC), glass (PRFV) and aramid (PRFA). Other types of fibers have been proposed in the literature, basalt (PRFB) and flax (PRFL) (Germain 2021).

To produce the fibers:

- The material is melted at high temperature (>1000c°).
- Cast by a thin perforated tank (capillary).
- Then suddenly it cooled by spraying water on it.
- Quickly stretched by drawing with continuously rotating rollers, this drawing process produces fibers at the micron scale.

In order for these fibers to have good adhesion with the resins, these steps are schematized in (Fig 02)(KILINÇARSLAN and TÜRKER 2020).

Fig.02. Production stages of fibers. Source: Investigation of Wooden Beam Behaviors Reinforced with Fiber Reinforced Polymers.2020

According to table.1, fibers have the following properties:

- A high tensile strength compared to steel; $R_{\text{fiber tensile}} (870-6000 \text{ MPa}) > R_{\text{steel tensile}} (240-690 \text{ MPa})$.
- High rigidity, they have an elongation at break of 9.0 -17.0% (PVA fibers) > steel (8.0-15%).
- Linear elastic behavior before rupture, carbon fibers are characterized by a high modulus of elasticity (290-400 GPa) the less the material deforms under stress and therefore, the more rigid it is.

Propreties	Fiber types				
	Carbon	Armide	PVA	Glass	Steel
Modulus of Elasticity (GPa)	<u>290-400</u>	62-142	8-28	70-86	200-210
Tensile Strength (MPa)	<u>2500-6000</u>	2410-3150	870-1350	2000-4500	240-690
Breaking Elongation (%)	0.3-1.8	1.5-4.4	<u>9.0-17.0</u>	2.5-5.0	8.0-15.0

Table.I. Range of mechanical properties of fibers. Source. Investigation of Wooden Beam Behaviors Reinforced with Fiber Reinforced Polymers.2020

Additionally, carbon fibers are resistant to water absorption, oxidation, creep, and relaxation (Guichard et al. 2018).

1.2. The matrix, constitution and properties

The role of the matrix is to maintain the cohesion between the fibers, to protect them from the external environment and to transmit the forces between them, made of either a thermoplastic or thermosetting resin. In engineering, thermosetting resins are composed of two types: polyester and epoxy (Cheung and Carey 2017).

As shown in table 2, Epoxy resin has higher:

- Tensile strength than polyester resins $R_{\text{epoxy tensile}} (55-130 \text{ MPa}) > R_{\text{polyester tensile}} (20-100 \text{ MPa})$.
- Rigidity, the deformation of both materials is less under stress.

Propreties	Polyester	Epoxy
Density (kg.m^{-3})	1000 - 1450	1100 - 1300
Tensile strength (MPa)	20 -100	55 - 130
Modulus of elasticity (GPa)	2.4 – 4.1	2.5 – 4.1
Elongation at break (%)	1 – 6.5	1.5 - 9

Table.2. Physical properties of thermosetting resins. Source. Carbon fibre reinforced polymers for strengthening of structural elements.2003

1.3. Properties of Fiber Reinforced Polymer composite

Fiber Reinforced Polymer is an advanced composite material that features outstanding properties such as high elastic modulus, high fatigue performance, high stiffness and strength-to-weight ratio and superior strength (Germain 2021). It is perfectly resistant to corrosion, and is easy to install because of its composition, as well as its wide variety of availability (Wang et al. 2020)

The mechanical properties of the composite depend on the matrix, the fibers used, their distribution and their direction. Composites generally contain 30 to 60% fibers. The fibers can be arranged in a unidirectional or multidirectional pattern, or in a particular grid; we call these composites unidirectional or multidirectional (ANDERS 2003). As a result, the tension strength of a unidirectional composite is greater along the direction of the fibers than perpendicularly (Guichard et al. 2018).

In a fiber-reinforced polymer composite, fiber quantity and type influence: see table.3

- The tensile strength of the composite, which can range from 520 MPa for the polymer reinforced with glass fibers to 2260 MPa for the source of polymer materials reinforced with carbon fibers.
- The value of the deformation at break varies between 1.0-1.5% (polymers reinforced with carbon fibers) up to 2.0-3.0% (Armidé fibers reinforced polymer).
- The ability to oppose deformations when subjected to mechanical stresses varies between 100-140 GPa (the carbon fiber reinforced polymer) up to 15-40 GPa (the PVA fiber reinforced polymer).

Composite	Tensile strength (Mpa)	Modulus of elasticity (GPa)	Elongation at break (%)
FRPCarbon	1020 - 2260	100-140	1.0 - 1.5
FRPArmide	700 - 1720	48 - 68	2.0 - 3.0
FRPPva	480 - 1500	15 - 40	1.2 - 1.6
FRPGlass	520 - 1400	20 - 40	1.5 - 3.0

Table.3. Properties of Fiber Reinforced Polymer Composites. Source. Renforcement des structures en bois à l'aide de polymère renforcé de fibres.2021

2. Timber beams reinforced with fiber-reinforced polymers

In structural construction, FRPs are used either to reinforce load-bearing members, or to improve bending and shear properties. Additionally, they can be used to repair damaged columns and beams in historical wooden houses to improve their resistance to external influences.

2.1. Techniques of reinforcing FRP with timber:

Three of the most common FRP-to-timber systems in the literature are:

- The externally bonded reinforcement (EBR) technique.
- The near-surface mounted (NSM) technique.
- The glued-in rods (GiR) technique.

FRP-to-wood systems	Description
<p>EBR</p> <p>Timber beam Adhesive FRP FRP laminates to timber</p>	It consists of FRP laminates bonded to the surface of the wooden element, which is generally used to reinforce existing wooden structures. The success of the technique relies heavily on the physical properties of the material used to attach this new reinforcement (Hutchinson 1992).
<p>NSM</p> <p>Timber beam FRP+Adhesive</p> <p>FRP bars into timber</p>	It is an effective method for strengthening newly constructed structures due to its greater efficiency in bending and shear strengthening, through better strain distribution, resulting in higher utilization of available strain. In the NSM system, the groove is cut close to the surface of the wood before the FRP bar is inserted with adhesive (Juvandes and Barbosa 2012).
<p>GiR</p> <p>Timber beam FRP+Adhesive</p> <p>FRP bars into timber</p>	has been used in construction engineering for decades based on steel rods. however, FRP rods have multiple advantages, such as improved mechanical properties, high strength, and increased compatibility with resin and wood that point to FRP (Erik and René 2008).

Table.4. Techniques for reinforcing FRP with wood. Source: The success of these techniques is attributed to the physical properties of FRP and its attachment material.

2.2. Adhesion and anchorage length

Adhesive is an important carrier for FRP glued wood system to form an effective bond and transfer shear stress and normal stress in interface contact and lap joint (Wang et al. 2020).

For adhesion and anchorage length, each wooden beam is covered with a single layer of fabric approximately 1.5 mm thick and stored for a 30-day cure. For long-term weathering, wood-FRP systems are exposed to weather for up to 40 months, while accelerated weathering follows EN 302-1 standard treatments, ranging from two hours to seven days exposure (Germain 2021).

Adhesives based on epoxy resin have been found to be the most suitable. All water-absorbing, two-component epoxy resin adhesives. This factor affects long-term performance and durability, and the development of interface corrosion. Sikadur 31 thixotropic epoxy adhesive, based on polyamine hardener, has particularly good resistance to moisture absorption. With this knowledge, the value not only of having low moisture absorption by the adhesive, but also the importance of combining high corrosion protection. This is achieved by incorporating MIO epoxy resin primer as part of the overall protection system (Hutchinson 1992).

2.3. FRP/timber beam ratio

The FRP-to-timber width ratio (the ratio of the width of the FRP to the width of the timber) is crucial for effective stress transfer. The low FRP to lumber width ratio results in non-uniform stress distribution across the width of the lumber and interfacial failure at a lower load level, resulting in higher stress in the bond at failure. Ideally, a width of 200 mm is recommended (Wang et al. 2020).

FRP has also been identified as a preferable feature throughout the timber beam, due to the fact that shear stress transfers more efficiently into the bond as we increase the length of the sheathing. According to Vahedian, Shrestha and Crews, a noticeable decrease in shear stress at failure was obtained as the length and width of the bond increased. This enhancement provides improved fracture behavior, leading to a more ductile collapse. This is because the shear stress is transferred more efficiently inside the bond and the reinforced timber beam will not completely collapse since the FRP prevents cracks from opening and limits local failure (Vahedian, Shrestha, and Crews 2017).

In the case of reinforcement, in the form of fabric or lamella, the number of layers to be applied is also important and is between one and three layers. Research has shown that the greater the number of layers, the greater the resistance. However, they also demonstrated that beyond three layers, this resistance tends to decrease, so a maximum of three layers is preferable (Germain 2021). Furthermore, if the bond thickness is large enough, the stiffness of the composite beams improves, which reduces the deflection of the reinforced beams. So a thickness of 1-5mm has also been identified as a desirable feature (Vahedian, Shrestha, and Crews 2019).

2.4. Expected effects of reinforcement

▪ Bending reinforcement

When it comes to evaluating the bending strength of a timber beam, the majority of experimentation is done with a four-point or three-point bend test, depending on the length of the beam. As a result, it is possible to measure the resistance of the beam, its displacement, and its stiffness.

The tension zone of a single-span simply supported beam is in the lower part of the section. The tensile stresses and the maximum axial deformations are localized on the underside of the beam (fig .03). Thus, in bending, tensile reinforcement is added mainly to the lower parts of a beam.

Fig.03. Reinforcement diagram of a beam subjected to three-point bending
Source. Renforcement des poutres en bois par un tissu de fibres de carbone (CFRP) 2018.

Reinforced beams exhibit an increase in bending strength both in the service state and in the ultimate state. The deformations (deflections) are weaker for the beams. Ahmad Yusof studied glulam panels reinforced on the upper and lower face with FRP sheets. Research has found that FRP-glulam beams not only exhibit significant strength increases, but also develop ductile compression failure rather than the brittle tensile failure typically associated with wood. (Yusof Ahmad 2013). An additional study of Douglas fir beams reinforced with GFRP (fiberglass) bars. Results revealed that failure modes changed from tension to compression failure (Gentile, Svecova, and Rizkalla 2002).

In terms of bending stiffness (EI , where E is the modulus of elasticity and I is the moment of inertia), experimentally determined values differ from theoretical values (the stiffness varies between 15% and 29% (Wang et al. 2020)) :

The EBR reinforcement method

The behavior of wooden stringers reinforced with GFRP sheets was studied by Gomez et al. The beams have been reinforced for shear and bending. Stiffness is improved from 5.5% to 52.8% with the proposed reinforcement (Gómez and Svecova 2008).

The NSM reinforcement method

Buell et al. conducted research on Douglas fir reinforced with two-way CFRP bars. In all reinforced beams, the ultimate bending resistance increased from 40% to 53% (Buell and Saadatmanesh 2005). While Johnson et al. evaluated three different configurations: 1) without reinforcement, 2) with a single NSM, 3) with two NSM. The results obtained show that reinforcement with two NSMs results in an increase in stiffness of approximately 10% at one NSM. Additionally, mid-span deflection at break is increased by 80%. All specimens reinforced with two NSMs demonstrated ductile failure in mid-span compression on the top of the beam. As compared to no reinforcement, two NSM reinforcements increase average load capacity by 44% to 63% (Johnsson, Blanksvärd, and Carolin 2007).

The GiR reinforcement method

The GiR reinforcement method increases the short-term bending load capacity of glulam beams by 49% to 63% on average (Johnsson, Blanksvärd, and Carolin 2007). In reinforced beams, the ultimate moment capacity and stiffness were reduced (Micelli, Scialpi, and La Tegola 2005). Additionally, Madhoushi et al. reported that the shear stress of the bar/adhesive interface is much greater than that of the adhesive/wood (Madhoushi and Ansell 2004). Raftery et al. concluded that the bonding behavior of bonded FRP rod reinforcement beams can be improved using the effects of stress concentrations (Raftery and Whelan 2014).

▪ **Ductility**

The ductility of a beam can be defined as its ability to withstand inelastic deformation without loss of its load bearing capacity before failure. The deformations can be deflections, curvatures or strains (Grace et al. 1998). Based on this definition, ductility can be expressed in terms of strain or energy absorption. The deflection ductility of a reinforced timber beam is increased by 28% to 51% compared to an unreinforced one (Buell and Saadatmanesh 2005).

The results obtained by Ahmed showed that the ductility increased as the percentage of FRP increased. The ductility was significantly improved when the highest ductility index based on the deflection method was 2.2, where the percentage increase was 37.5%, while the highest ductility index based on the energy method was 3.2, where the percentage increase was 88.2%. The maximum ductility index for FRP surfaces was found to be 0.3% (Yusof Ahmad 2013).

Experiments showed that the failure of FRP to strengthen timber beams occurred when the maximum stress was about 0.6%, which is about half of the breaking stress of FRP sheets. Therefore, the ultimate bending strength of a reinforced timber beam would not solely depend on the tensile strength of the fiber composites; but instead, the mechanical properties of wood should always be considered for ultimate and serviceability limit state designs (Vahedian, Shrestha, and Crews 2019).

Conclusion

Problems related to low efficiency of structural elements, increased overload and degradation with aging are common in the construction industry. These pathologies have led to the development of new structural reinforcement techniques. Timber structures require repairs in various situations to make them suitable for further use, while in other cases they require reinforcement to increase the load-bearing capacity of their structural elements. The application of fiber reinforced polymers is a solution method that can be used to reinforce timber beams in cases where the load capacity and rigidity must be high.

Through the analysis of the reviews, the main conclusions of this study can be summarized as follows:

- Due to the high mechanical properties of FRP ($R_{\text{tensile}} = 2260 \text{ MPa}$) and its superiority to steel ($R_{\text{tensile}} = 400 \text{ MPa}$), in addition to its high stiffness-to-weight ratio (10 to 15 times higher than steel) and long-term behavior, FRP has been recommended as a good alternative to steel as a reinforcement material for timber beams.

- Reinforced on the underside with FRP sheets, the ultimate bending strength of the beam increases from: 5.5% to 52.8% (the EBR technique), 40% to 53% (the NSM technique) and 49% to 63% (for technical GiR). By contrast, mid-span deflection decreases, resulting in higher stiffness values (between 31% and 64%).
- The deflection ductility of a reinforced timber beam has increased from 28% to 51%. This improvement allows for better fracture behavior obtained when the length and width (200 mm is recommended) of the reinforced polymer fibers increase, leading to a more ductile collapse. Consequently, FRP transfers shear stresses more evenly and prevents cracks from opening in the reinforced timber beam.

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